

UDC: 1.091.101.3

THE EMERGENCE OF CROSS-CULTURE IN CENTRAL ASIA

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Abstract: The article examines the formation and development of cross-culture as a multifunctional phenomenon using the example of the Turkic (Uzbek) and Iranian (Tajik) cultural substrate. Using specific examples, the author of the article proves that cross-culture is a universal phenomenon. It is inherent in all peoples of the earth. Any culture, no matter in what form or form it appears, has a transnational imprint. It does not exist in a sterile pure form either in past or present cultural formations, especially in the era of digitalization and informatization of society. Cultures such as Greek, Roman, Iranian Anglo-Saxon, Arab, etc. were essentially cross-cultural.

Keywords: cross-culture, Uzbek culture, Tajik culture, bilingualism, matrix, cultural education, Eastern culture, Western culture.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается формирование и становление кросс-культуры как полифункциональное явление на примере тюркском (узбекском) и иранском (таджикском) культурном субстрате. На конкретных примерах, автор статьи доказывает, что кросс-культура - явление общечеловеческое. Она присуща всем народам земли. Всякая культура, в какой бы форме и виде она не проявилась, имеет транснациональный отпечаток. Не существует в стерильно чистом виде ни в прошлых, ни в настоящих культурных образованиях, особенно в эпоху цифровизации и информатизации общества. Такие культуры как греческая, римская, иранская англо-сакская, арабская и т. д. по существу были кросс-культурными.

Ключевые слова: кросс-культура, узбекская культура, таджикская культура, билингвизм, матрица, культурное образование, культура Востока, культура Запада.

In the 19th century, in the era of digitalization and informatization of all areas of human activity, the problem of understanding and perceiving culture becomes extremely important and relevant. After all, this sphere of human existence is capable (and should be capable) of bringing a person out of the natural limitations of existence.

Culture is a general concept. In real life, it receives various modifications. It is no coincidence that we say: political, artistic, moral, religious, industrial, agricultural culture, and so on. It is multifunctional in nature, that is, it performs many tasks in the life of society, and one of them (perhaps the most important) is the “humanization” of people through its material and spiritual foundations.

When we say “national culture”, this is, in fact, the correct formulation. It has its own specifics, features: module, structure, standards. These concepts cannot be ignored, just like the national language.

We do not know sterilely pure Greek, English, German, French, Russian, Chinese, or Arabic cultures, not to mention modern American. One way or another, directly or indirectly, each of them is naturally historically formed and developed in connection with the other. This phenomenon is called cross-cultural education based on a single unique material and spiritual matrix.

In this regard, the Iranian-Turkic, in our case Uzbek and Tajik (Persian) cultural matrix is of particular interest. It should be said that in understanding and interpreting its formation, formation and genesis, the narrow ethnic approach has not yet been overcome. However, the real world of culture, including national culture, with its diversity and dynamism, is revealed not only by social, but also by the laws of integration and communicative existence of individuals and society as a whole.

The historical and political situations in which agricultural (Persian) and nomadic (Turkic) ethnic groups found themselves in the distant past ultimately led

to interpenetration or, as they say in modern cultural studies, a dialogue of cultures. Of course, the ethnic background underlying this process was not always fully realized and could not be perceived as a confrontation between cultural positions.

However, the main thing here is that, regardless of purely tribal and ethnic interests, development led to an awareness of the need for mutual acceptance of nomadic and agricultural (later urban) cultures. This, in turn, contributed to the development of a specific synthesis and the creation of a single matrix acceptable for both Turkic and Iranian ethnic groups (in this case, Uzbek and Tajik).

Poetry, music, dance and other types of arts, different customs and traditions were synthesized into a single culture, contributed to the rapprochement of ethnic groups and peoples while preserving their originality.

The matrix of Iranian-Turkic culture obviously received a clear design under the Ghaznavid systems of government (10-11th centuries), when the Persian language was adopted not only as the main means of communication between different ethnic groups, but also as a specific communication channel through which exchanges took place spiritual and material values between tribes and clans. Among its content components are the folk calendar holiday Navruz, as well as a system of moral, aesthetic and legal norms, including caring and respect for the flora and fauna and nature in general.

The single matrix of Uzbek and Tajik culture led to bilingualism. Bilingualism as a cross-cultural phenomenon should be interpreted in a broad sense, since it is primarily a product of the spiritual unity of different ethnic groups. Thus, the classical literature of Iran and Turan has been considered one for thousands of years. It is no coincidence that not only the formal side of their poetry is identical and common (structure, poetics, expressive and figurative means, metrical systems of versification, and so on), but also the internal components (ideas, ideals, desires and aspirations).

Thinkers and poets, rulers and officials of the Turkic-Iranian world strongly supported and encouraged the creativity of bilingual poets. In his famous treatise

“Majolis un-nafois” Alisher Navoi cites more than 25 names of famous authors and speaks with admiration and approval of their works. By the way, Navoi himself was bilingual and composed magnificent poems in both Turkic and Persian. In his work “Judgement on Two Languages,” Navoi, comparing Persian with Turkic (Uzbek), spoke about the need for parallel development of both.

In this context, the emergence of the poetic genre shiru shakar (literally “milk and sugar” - a direction in which the lines are alternately stated in Persian and Uzbek) is important. This phenomenon indicates the cross-cultural nature of the spiritual life of the two ethnic groups. Shiru shakar has become widespread not only in poetry, but also in the songwriting of a number of Uzbek and Tajik performers, both past and present.

It is known that the main trigger for confrontation between different ethnic groups in the region since ancient times has been pastures, territories, nomadism and water sources. Sometimes they turned into Gordian knots, which were often “cut” with the help of culture and its means.

The fact is that from ancient times the Turkic-Iranian cultural matrix was built not on struggle and hatred, but on the principles of mutual assistance and support at different stages of historical and sustainable development. That is why issues of friendship, spiritual unity, mutual understanding in Uzbek cross-culture have acquired value significance and are still considered necessary for fruitful cooperation of peoples and ethnic groups in Central Asia.

It should be noted that the Iranian-Turkic matrix is based on a dialogue between “I” and “you”, “we” and “you”. We can call this the greatest achievement of cross-cultural education, because this is how the interdependence of the Turkic and Iranian ethnic groups crystallized and acquired a spiritual character in the face of harsh reality.

True, at a certain period of time, attempts were made to exclude its Persian-Tajik component from the Uzbek cultural matrix. As a result, the work of such great figures as Rudaki, Ferdowsi, Nizami, Amir Khusraw Dehlavi, Bedil, Sanoi

Ghaznavi, Attor, Rumi, Saadi, Hafiz, and hundreds of other representatives of the culture of the region was practically erased and is only now gradually returning to the lives of contemporaries. In a cross-culture, division according to the principles of “mine” and “yours”, “ours” and “yours” does not work. Spirituality, regardless of ethnic and linguistic components, belongs to all peoples living in the same cultural space. This is not a bone of contention that can cause hostility between ethnic groups. On the contrary, it has always emanated and continues to emanate from the unifying, creative principles of human existence.

Culture evokes not only the needs of man in people, but also of nations and peoples in each other. Therefore, at the present stage of state building, society needs a broad ideological and cultural outlook, and the study of historical materials is mandatory. All this would make it possible to overcome the old narrow ethnic ideas that stemmed from the concepts of the past.

Cross-culture is composed of national languages, community of many traditions, traits, character, psychology, with the help of which ethnic groups maintain their natural-historical unity, territorial integrity and in parts. After all, it accumulates universal humanity in its essence, for it does not fence itself off, does not alienate itself from others, but strives for communication and mutual enrichment.

Speaking about language, the question involuntarily arises about the role of Persian in the enrichment of Uzbek, and then Turkic (Uzbek) in the development of Tajik. Persian words form a kind of linguistic and poetic basis of our language in the same way as French and Latin terms form the basis of the cultural vocabulary of Russian - starting with art (music, theater, painting, literature, and so on) and ending with the names and titles of bit objects.

It is no coincidence that a saying arose among the people: “Forsi shakar ast, Turks hunar ast,” which can be translated as follows: “The Persian language is sugar, and the Turkic language is art.”

The amazing thing is that for centuries the Turkic languages and Persian lived together and collaborated, complementing and enriching each other. Therefore,

expanding the field of the Tajik (Persian) language in the modern conditions of Uzbekistan means, firstly, a more in-depth study of national culture; secondly, strengthening the spiritual closeness of Uzbeks and Tajiks for the sake of the well-being of both peoples.

Proof of this can be, for example, a Persian letter from Sahibkiran to the French king, preserved in Persian, which at that time served as an international language instrument. The first sentence of this letter began with a Turkish sentence in the form “Amir Temur Koragon’s word”. [1]

The historical relationship and mutual enrichment of the Turkic and Persian - Uzbek and Tajik languages can be clearly seen in the example of their phonetic bases. Tajik teachings M. Fayzov (1935-2010) at one time tried to draw up a phonetic map of Tajiks and Uzbeks. It turns out that the phonetic difference between Tajiks and Uzbeks living in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan and outside these Republics is not very significant. Hence the rhythmic-intonation identity in song art, which always amazes listeners. It is difficult, for example, to determine the ethnicity of famous modern pop singers when they sing their songs in Tajik or Uzbek. These specific examples indicate that the basic parameters of cross-culture are preserved in modern culture.

The nature of thought is such that it, like any other phenomenon, is subject to aging, and therefore to disappearance. The finitude of any mental construct, wise or foolish, is a dead end, regardless of who it is expressed by, a great man or a mere mortal. Therefore, every time you have to struggle to get out of your own impasse. This statement does not mean that you need to overthink, because without this it is impossible to exist on “this eternal land,” as B. Okudzhava wrote.

It has long been known that any mental construction in the form of a concept is relative in nature. Over time, due to socio-historical changes, scientific and technical ideas of people, it will either narrow or expand in content, otherwise it may lose its original meaning or simply become an anachronism. Many concepts in the era of digitalization and information, intercontinental trade, economic, financial,

information connections have become extremely unstable, and sometimes contradict reality.

It is known from history that in a difficult situation, when threats to the Motherland and the fate of the people intensified, it was the selfless patriots of the nation - representatives of the intelligentsia, poets and writers, artists, workers in the field of spirituality and enlightenment who courageously entered the arena with an awakened heart and soul. “At present, when our country is entering a new, high stage of its development, we need, like water and air, mature personnel like our Jadid ancestors, who, along with mastering the achievements of Western science, are also brought up in the spirit of national values,” noted Shavkat Mirziyoyev. [2]

As for cross-culture, in the coordinate system of modern human existence and new social, political, cultural paradigms, it determines the general trends in the spiritual development of society and acts as a way of self-affirmation of an ethnic group, people and personality.

In the era of digital civilization, national culture cannot be curbed; it will be limited only by national standards, stereotypes, canons, traditions, and so on. It must develop in the general continuous flow of universal human culture. Otherwise, it “dries up” on its own roots, without becoming part of the world heritage.

Reference

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